

MODELLING OF SANDWICH BEAMS WITH COMPOSITE LAMINATED FACINGS AND COMPRESSIBLE ORTHOTROPIC CORE

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INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures, consisting of a core covered by facings, are frequently used in marine, aviation and civil engineering applications because of their high bending stiffness-to-weight ratio. Many of the modern sandwich beams, panels and shells are made of composite laminated facings and a flexible core. The complexity of the stress-strain state has yielded a numerous number of sandwich structures models. Until recently, most of the models, that appear in the research reports are based on the incompressible core models [1-4]. The reliability of such models in case of soft core is dubious. Thus, at present, analyses of modern sandwich structures require the use of advanced computational models [5-8]. As this takes place, the beam model is a best suitable tool for an initial investigation of more elaborate sandwich models of the panels and shells. The computational model of sandwich beam with laminated facings and compressible orthotropic core is considered in the present paper.

SANDWICH BEAM MODEL

Let us consider the prismatic sandwich beam with a rectangular-shaped cross-section (Fig.1). The sandwich beam consists of two laminated composite facings and orthotropic core.

Fig.1. Dimensions and loads of the sandwich beam

Let us relate the beam to the system of Cartesian coordinates x, y, z . Let the x -axis passes through the centroids of the core cross-section. It is the longitudinal axis of the beam. The y, z – axes are located perpendicularly to the x -axis as in Fig.1. The beam length is denoted by l and the width of the beam cross-section is denoted by b . The core thickness is δ . The thicknesses of the upper and lower facings are t_1 and t_2 respectively. The beam is subjected to distributed loads p and q (Fig.1). Note, that in general case p and q are functions of variable x only. Hereafter, we shall assume, that all functions describing the stress-strain state of a sandwich beam do not depend on coordinate z . This enables to use the equations of plane elasticity theory for the development of the beam model including the facing model and the core model. The one-dimensional equations of the sandwich beam will be obtained from the two-dimensional elasticity theory equations by using hypotheses.

Core model

Consider the beam core. Let us take a look at the set of the equations of the elasticity theory for an orthotropic medium describing the stress-strain state of the core. The equilibrium equations have the form

$$\partial \sigma_x / \partial x + \partial \tau_{xy} / \partial y = 0 \quad \partial \tau_{xy} / \partial x + \partial \sigma_y / \partial y = 0 \quad (1)$$

where σ_x , σ_y are the normal stresses and τ_{xy} is the shear stress (Fig. 2)

Fig.2. Stresses and displacements in the core

The stresses are related to the strains by Hooke's law in the form

$$e_x = \sigma_x / E_x - \mu_{xy} \sigma_y / E_y \quad e_y = \sigma_y / E_y - \mu_{yx} \sigma_x / E_x \quad (2)$$

$$e_{xy} = \tau_{xy} / G_{xy} \quad (3)$$

Here e_x , e_y are the normal strains, e_{xy} is the shear strain, E_x , E_y are the moduli of elasticity, G_{xy} is the shear modulus, μ_{xy} and μ_{yx} are the Poisson's ratios.

The normal and shear strains are related to displacements u_x and u_y (Fig. 2) along the x and y coordinates by the following geometric relations

$$e_x = \partial u_x / \partial x \quad e_y = \partial u_y / \partial y \quad e_{xy} = \partial u_x / \partial y + \partial u_y / \partial x \quad (4)$$

The equations (1)-(4) include two independent coordinates x , y . In order to derive the one-dimensional equations of the beam core we use the hypothesis. Resolving Eq.(2) about the stresses, we obtain

$$\sigma_x = \bar{E}_x (e_x + \mu_{xy} e_y) \quad \sigma_y = \bar{E}_y (e_y + \mu_{yx} e_x) \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{E}_x = E_x / (1 - \mu_{xy} \mu_{yx})$ and $\bar{E}_y = E_y / (1 - \mu_{xy} \mu_{yx})$.

For the core the hypothesis assumes that the modulus of elasticity in the longitudinal direction E_x and the Poisson's ratio μ_{xy} are equal to zero. It follows from Eq.(5) that $\sigma_x = 0$ and $\sigma_y = E_y e_y$. For $\sigma_x = 0$, the first relationship in Eq.(1) yields $\partial \tau_{xy} / \partial y = 0$. Then, the shear stress takes the form

$$\tau_{xy} = \tau(x) \quad (6)$$

Now determine the σ_y distribution over the core thickness. Substituting the shear stress of Eq.(6) in the second of Eqs.(1), we have $\partial \sigma_y / \partial y = -d\tau_x / dx$. Integrating the obtained equation with respect to y we arrive at

$$\sigma_y = \sigma - y d\tau_x / dx \quad (7)$$

Here, $\sigma(x) = \sigma_y(y = 0)$ is the stress, acting along a perpendicular to the x axis (Fig.2). Let us derive the u_y displacement. Substituting $e_y = \sigma_y / E_y$ in the second of Eqs.(4), we get $\partial u_y / \partial y = \sigma_y / E_y$. Integrating this equation with respect to y and taking into account Eq.(7), we obtain

$$u_y = v + \frac{1}{E_y} \left(\sigma_y - \frac{y^2}{2} \frac{d\tau}{dx} \right) \quad (8)$$

where $v(x) = u_y(y = 0)$ is the deflection of the points located at the x -axis (Fig. 2).

Completing the advent of the core model let us find the distribution of the u_x displacement over the core thickness. Substituting the e_{xy} strain of Eq.(3) and $\tau_{xy} = \tau$ in the third of Eqs.(4), we get $\partial u_x / \partial y = \tau / G_{xy} - \partial u_y / \partial x$. Integrating the obtained equation over y and taking into account Eq.(8) we arrive at

$$u_x = u + \frac{\tau}{G_{xy}} y - \left[\frac{dv}{dx} y - \frac{1}{E_y} \left(\frac{d\sigma}{dx} \frac{y^2}{2} - \frac{y^3}{6} \frac{d^2\tau}{dx^2} \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

Here, $u(x) = u_x (y = 0)$ is the x -displacement of the points located at the x -axis (Fig. 2).

The equations (6), (7), (8), (9) prescribe the stress and displacement distribution over the core thickness. Thus, the stress-strain state of the compressible core is determined by $\sigma(x)$, $\tau(x)$, $u(x)$ and $v(x)$.

Facing model

Consider the upper facing (Fig.3). The line with $y = (\delta + t_1)/2$ is the middle line of the upper facing.

Fig.3. Stresses and displacements in the upper facing

The set of the equations of the elasticity theory for an orthotropic medium describing of the stress-strain state of the upper facing includes equilibrium equations

$$\partial\sigma_{1x}/\partial x + \partial\tau_{1xy}/\partial y = 0 \quad \partial\tau_{1xy}/\partial x + \partial\sigma_{1y}/\partial y = 0 \quad (10)$$

constitutive relations (Hooke's law)

$$e_{1x} = \sigma_{1x}/E_{1x} - \mu_{1xy} \sigma_{1y}/E_{1y} \quad e_{1y} = \sigma_{1y}/E_{1y} - \mu_{1yx} \sigma_{1x}/E_{1x} \quad e_{1xy} = \tau_{1xy}/G_{1xy} \quad (11)$$

and strain displacement relations

$$e_{1x} = \partial u_{1x}/\partial x \quad e_{1y} = \partial u_{1y}/\partial y \quad e_{1xy} = \partial u_{1x}/\partial y + \partial u_{1y}/\partial x \quad (12)$$

In Eqs. (10), (11), (12) σ_{1x} , σ_{1y} , τ_{1xy} are the stresses (Fig. 3), e_{1x} , e_{1y} , e_{1xy} are the strains, E_{1x} , E_{1y} , G_{1xy} are the moduli of elasticity, μ_{1xy} , μ_{1yx} are the Poisson's ratios and u_{1x} , u_{1y} are the displacements (Fig. 3).

The one-dimensional equations for the facing can be obtained from the two-dimensional equations (10)-(12) by using two hypotheses [9]. First of them holds, that the facing material must be regarded as absolutely rigid over the facing thickness. Then, we must take $e_{1y} = 0$. Because in the general case stresses σ_{1x} and σ_{1y} are nonzero, it follows from the second of Eqs.(11) that $E_{1y} \rightarrow \infty$ and $\mu_{1yx} = 0$. Then the first of Eqs.(11) yields $\sigma_{1x} = E_{1x} e_{1x}$. The second hypothesis asserts that the shear stress and the shear strain must be averaged over the facing thickness, i. e. $\tau_{1xy} = Q_1/(t_1 b)$, $e_{1xy} = \psi_1$. Here, Q_1 is the transverse shear force applied to the middle line of the upper facing (Fig.4) and

$$\psi_1(x) = \frac{1}{t_1} \int_{\delta/2}^{\delta/2+t_1} e_{1xy} dy \quad (13)$$

is the thickness-averaged shear strain.

Fig.4. Forces, moment and displacements in the upper facing

Now, determine the distributions of the u_{1y} , u_{1x} displacements over the upper facing thickness. For $e_{1y} = 0$, the second geometric relationship in Eqs.(12) yields

$$u_{1y} = v_1(x) \quad (14)$$

where $v_1(x)$ is the upper facing deflection (Fig.4). Then, replacing e_{1xy} with ψ_1 in the third of Eqs.(12) and taking into account Eq.(14), we have $\partial u_{1x} / \partial y = \psi_1 - dv_1 / dx$. Integrating the obtained equation with respect to y , we arrive at

$$u_{1x} = u_1 + \theta_1(y - (\delta + t_1)/2) \quad (15)$$

Here, $u_1 = u_{1x}$ ($y = (\delta + t_1)/2$) is the displacement of the points of the middle line of the upper facing along the x -direction (Fig.4) and

$$\theta_1 = \psi_1 - dv_1 / dx \quad (16)$$

is the rotation angle of the cross section of the upper facing.

Let us derive the geometric relationships of the facing model. Substituting Eq.(15) in the first of Eqs.(12), we obtain

$$e_{1x} = \varepsilon_1 + k_1(y - (\delta + t_1)/2) \quad (17)$$

$$\text{where} \quad \varepsilon_1 = du_1 / dx \quad k_1 = d\theta_1 / dx \quad (18)$$

Here, ε_1 is the normal strain of the middle line and k_1 is the curvature change of the middle line. Let us obtain the equation for the shear strain ψ_1 . From Eqs. (16) we have

$$\psi_1 = \theta_1 + dv_1 / dx \quad (19)$$

The equations (18) and (19) are the required set of the geometric relationship of the upper facing model. Substituting the strain of Eq.(17) in Hook's law $\sigma_{1x} = E_{1x}e_{1x}$, we arrive at

$$\sigma_{1x} = E_{1x}[\varepsilon_1 + k_1(y - (\delta + t_1)/2)] \quad (20)$$

To describe the stress state of the upper facing, it is more natural to consider axial force, bending moment and transverse force (Fig.4) applied to the middle line

$$N_1 = b \int_{\delta/2}^{\delta/2+t_1} \sigma_{1x} dy \quad M_1 = b \int_{\delta/2}^{\delta/2+t_1} \sigma_{1x}(y - (\delta + t_1)/2) dy \quad Q_1 = b \int_{\delta/2}^{\delta/2+t_1} \tau_{1x} dy \quad (21)$$

Substituting the stress of Eq.(20) in the first and second of Eqs.(21), we have the following constitutive equations

$$N_1 = B_1 \varepsilon_1 + C_1 k_1 \quad M_1 = C_1 \varepsilon_1 + D_1 k_1 \quad (22)$$

$$\text{where } B_1 = b \int_{\delta/2}^{\delta/2+t_1} E_{1x} dy \quad D_1 = b \int_{\delta/2}^{\delta/2+t_1} E_{1x}(y - (\delta + t_1)/2)^2 dy \quad C_1 = b \int_{\delta/2}^{\delta/2+t_1} E_{1x}(y - (\delta + t_1)/2) dy \quad (23)$$

Here, B_1 is the axial stiffness, D_1 is the bending stiffness and C_1 is the coupling stiffness of the upper facing. Now derive the constitutive equation for the transverse shear force Q_1 . With this aim, use Eq.(13) for the thickness-averaged shear strain. This equation is

transformed, with due regard for $e_{1xy} = \tau_{1xy} / G_{1xy}$, to the form $\psi_1 = \frac{1}{t_1} \int_{\delta/2}^{\delta/2+t_1} \frac{\tau_{1xy}}{G_{1xy}} dy$.

Substituting there $\tau_{1xy} = Q_1 / (t_1 b)$, we obtain

$$Q_1 = K_1 \psi_1 \quad (24)$$

$$\text{where} \quad K_1 = t_1^2 b \left(\int_{\delta/2}^{\delta/2+t_1} \frac{dy}{G_{1xy}} \right)^{-1} \quad (25)$$

Here, K_1 is the transverse shear stiffness.

Thus, the constitutive equations have the form of Eqs.(22) and Eq.(24). The coefficients B_1 , D_1 , C_1 and K_1 determine the upper facing stiffnesses and contain all the information on the upper facing structure and the mechanical properties of the components. The moduli E_{1x} and G_{1xy} are certain smooth or step-wise functions of variable y .

Let us derive the one-dimensional equilibrium equations of the upper facing. The static boundary conditions on the surface $y = \delta/2 + t_1$ can be written in the form

$$\sigma_{1y}(x, \delta/2 + t_1) = p \quad \tau_{1xy}(x, \delta/2 + t_1) = 0 \quad (26)$$

Multiplying Eqs.(10) by b and then integrating over the upper facing thickness and taking into account Eqs.(21) and (26), we obtain

$$dN_1/dx - b\tau_{1xy}(x, \delta/2) = 0 \quad dQ_1/dx + bp - b\sigma_{1y}(x, \delta/2) = 0 \quad (27)$$

Here, $\tau_{1xy}(x, \delta/2)$ and $\sigma_{1y}(x, \delta/2)$ are the contact stresses acting between the upper facing and the core. Now multiply the first of Eqs.(10) by $b(y - (\delta + t_1)/2)$ and integrate with respect to y in the range from $\delta/2$ to $\delta/2 + t_1$. Taking into account Eqs.(21) and (26), we get

$$dM_1/dx - Q_1 - b(t_1/2)\tau_{1xy}(x, \delta/2) = 0 \quad (28)$$

The equations (27) and (28) are the equilibrium equations of the upper facing.

Thus, we have constructed the model of the upper facing. The set of equations describing the stress-strain state of the upper facing includes equilibrium equations (27), (28), constitutive relationships (22), (24) and geometric equations (18), (19).

Let us derive a set of equations including only displacements u_1 , v_1 and rotation angle θ_1 . Substituting sequentially Eqs.(18), (19), (22), (24) into Eqs.(27) and (28), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} B_1 d^2 u_1 / dx^2 + C_1 d^2 \theta_1 / dx^2 - b \tau_{1xy}(x, \delta/2) &= 0 \\ K_1 d^2 v_1 / dx^2 + K_1 d \theta_1 / dx + bp - b \sigma_{1xy}(x, \delta/2) &= 0 \\ C_1 d^2 u_1 / dx^2 - K_1 d v_1 / dx + D_1 d^2 \theta_1 / dx^2 - K_1 \theta_1 + b(t_1/2) \tau_{1xy}(x, \delta/2) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Now consider the lower facing (Fig.5). The line with $y = -(\delta + t_2)/2$ is the middle line of the lower facing.

Fig.5. Forces, moment and displacements in the lower facing

The deduction of the equations describing the stress-strain state of the lower facing, completely coincides with the deduction of the similar equations for the upper facing. Therefore, omitting intermediate manipulations, we shall write down at once the basic equations for the lower facing. We have the equilibrium equations

$$\begin{aligned} dN_2/dx + b\tau_{2xy}(x, -\delta/2) = 0 \quad dQ_2/dx + b\sigma_{2y}(x, -\delta/2) - bq = 0 \\ dM_2/dx - Q_2 + b(t_2/2)\tau_{2xy}(x, -\delta/2) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

constitutive relations

$$N_2 = B_2 \varepsilon_2 + C_2 k_2 \quad M_2 = C_2 \varepsilon_2 + D_2 k_2 \quad Q_2 = K_2 \psi_2 \quad (31)$$

geometric equations

$$\varepsilon_2 = du_2/dx \quad k_2 = d\theta_2/dx \quad \psi_2 = \theta_2 + dv_2/dx \quad (32)$$

Here, N_2 , Q_2 are the axial and transverse forces and M_2 is the bending moment (Fig.5) applied to the middle line of the lower facing, ε_2 , ψ_2 , k_2 are the generalized strains, u_2 , v_2 are the displacement of the lower middle line (Fig.5), θ_2 is the rotation angle, $\tau_{2xy}(x, -\delta/2)$ and $\sigma_{2y}(x, -\delta/2)$ are the contact stresses acting between the lower facing and the core. The stiffness coefficients B_2 , D_2 , C_2 and K_2 have the following form

$$\begin{aligned}
B_2 &= b \int_{-(\delta/2+t_2)}^{-\delta/2} E_{2x} dy & C_2 &= b \int_{-(\delta/2+t_2)}^{-\delta/2} E_{2x} (y + (\delta + t_2)/2) dy \\
D_2 &= b \int_{-(\delta/2+t_2)}^{-\delta/2} E_{2x} (y + (\delta + t_2)/2)^2 dy & K_2 &= t_2^2 b \left(\int_{-(\delta/2+t_2)}^{-\delta/2} \frac{dy}{G_{2xy}} \right)^{-1}
\end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

The distributions of the u_{1y} , u_{2y} displacements over the lower facing thickness are

$$u_{2y} = v_2 \tag{34}$$

$$u_{2x} = u_2 + \theta_2 (y + (\delta + t_2)/2) \tag{35}$$

The equilibrium equations including displacements and rotation angle have the form

$$\begin{aligned}
B_2 d^2 u_2 / dx^2 + C_2 d^2 \theta_2 / dx^2 + b \tau_{2xy}(x, -\delta/2) &= 0 \\
K_2 d^2 v_2 / dx^2 + K_2 d \theta_2 / dx - b q + b \sigma_{2xy}(x, -\delta/2) &= 0 \\
C_2 d^2 u_2 / dx^2 - K_2 d v_2 / dx + D_2 d^2 \theta_2 / dx^2 - K_2 \theta_2 + b (t_2/2) \tau_{2xy}(x, -\delta/2) &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

Thus, we have constructed the models of the both facings.

Contact conditions

Consider the contact conditions occurring on the lines of the demarcation between the core and the facings $y = \delta/2$ and $y = -\delta/2$. Primarily let us write the contact conditions for the displacements. We have

$$u_{1y}(x, \delta/2) = u_y(x, \delta/2) \quad u_{2y}(x, -\delta/2) = u_y(x, -\delta/2) \tag{37}$$

$$u_{1x}(x, \delta/2) = u_x(x, \delta/2) \quad u_{2x}(x, -\delta/2) = u_x(x, -\delta/2) \tag{38}$$

Substituting Eqs. (8), (14), (34) in Eqs. (37), we obtain

$$v_1 = v + \frac{1}{E_y} \left(\sigma \frac{\delta}{2} - \frac{\delta^2}{8} \frac{d\tau}{dx} \right) \quad v_2 = v + \frac{1}{E_y} \left(-\sigma \frac{\delta}{2} - \frac{\delta^2}{8} \frac{d\tau}{dx} \right) \tag{39}$$

Combining v_1 and v_2 , we get

$$v = \frac{v_1 + v_2}{2} + \frac{1}{E_y} \frac{\delta^2}{8} \frac{d\tau}{dx} \tag{40}$$

The relationship (40) defines the deflections of the core points located at the x -axis. Subtracting the second relationship in Eq. (39) from the first, we receive

$$\sigma = E_y (v_1 - v_2) / \delta \tag{41}$$

The obtained equation defines the normal stress acting along a perpendicular to the beam longitudinal axis.

Consider the condition, Eq.(38). Substituting Eqs.(9), (15), (35) in Eqs.(38), we obtain

$$u_1 - \theta_1 \frac{t_1}{2} = u + \frac{\tau}{G_{xy}} \frac{\delta}{2} - \left[\frac{dv}{dx} \frac{\delta}{2} + \frac{1}{E_y} \left(\frac{d\sigma}{dx} \frac{\delta^2}{8} - \frac{\delta^3}{48} \frac{d^2\tau}{dx^2} \right) \right] \tag{42}$$

$$u_2 + \theta_2 \frac{t_2}{2} = u - \frac{\tau}{G_{xy}} \frac{\delta}{2} - \left[-\frac{dv}{dx} \frac{\delta}{2} + \frac{1}{E_y} \left(\frac{d\sigma}{dx} \frac{\delta^2}{8} + \frac{\delta^3}{48} \frac{d^2\tau}{dx^2} \right) \right] \tag{43}$$

Combining Eq.(42) and Eq.(43), we have

$$u = \frac{u_1 + u_2}{2} - \frac{1}{4} (\theta_1 t_1 - \theta_2 t_2) + \frac{1}{E_y} \frac{\delta^2}{8} \frac{d\sigma}{dx} \tag{44}$$

The latter relationship defines the horizontal displacements of the core points located at the x -axis. Subtracting Eq.(43) from Eq.(42) and taking into account Eq.(40), we obtain

$$\frac{1}{E_y} \frac{\delta^3}{12} \frac{d^2\tau}{dx^2} = -u_1 + \theta_1 \frac{t_1}{2} + u_2 + \theta_2 \frac{t_2}{2} + \frac{\tau}{G_{xy}} - \frac{\delta}{2} \frac{dv_1}{dx} - \frac{\delta}{2} \frac{dv_2}{dx} \tag{45}$$

The obtained equation is the basic governing equation for the core.

Now, consider the contact conditions for the stresses. In the contact lines we have

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_{1xy}(x, \delta/2) &= \tau_{xy}(x, \delta/2) & \sigma_{1y}(x, \delta/2) &= \sigma_y(x, \delta/2) \\ \tau_{2xy}(x, -\delta/2) &= \tau_{xy}(x, -\delta/2) & \sigma_{2y}(x, -\delta/2) &= \sigma_y(x, -\delta/2)\end{aligned}\quad (46)$$

Substituting Eqs.(6), (7), (41) in Eqs.(46), we get

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_{1xy}(x, \delta/2) &= \tau & \sigma_{1y}(x, \delta/2) &= E_y(v_1 - v_2)/\delta - (\delta/2)d\tau/dx \\ \tau_{2xy}(x, -\delta/2) &= \tau & \sigma_{2y}(x, -\delta/2) &= E_y(v_1 - v_2)/\delta + (\delta/2)d\tau/dx\end{aligned}\quad (47)$$

General form of governing equations

Let us replace the contact stresses involved in Eqs. (29), (36) by means of Eqs. (47). Then, let us combine Eqs. (29), (45), (36) in the unified set of the equations. After some manipulations, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}B_1 d^2 u_1 / dx^2 + C_1 d^2 \theta_1 / dx^2 &= b\tau \\ K_1 d^2 v_1 / dx^2 &= bE_y v_1 / \delta - bE_y v_2 / \delta - (b\delta/2)d\tau/dx - K_1 d\theta_1 / dx - bp \\ C_1 d^2 u_1 / dx^2 + D_1 d^2 \theta_1 / dx^2 &= K_1 \theta_1 - bt_1 \tau / 2 + K_1 dv_1 / dx \\ (\delta^3 / 12E_y) d^2 \tau / dx^2 &= -u_1 + \theta_1 t_1 / 2 + u_2 + \theta_2 t_2 / 2 + \delta\tau / G_{xy} - \\ &\quad - (\delta/2)dv_1 / dx - (\delta/2)dv_2 / dx\end{aligned}\quad (48)$$

$$\begin{aligned}B_2 d^2 u_2 / dx^2 + C_2 d^2 \theta_2 / dx^2 &= -b\tau \\ K_2 d^2 v_2 / dx^2 &= -bE_y v_1 / \delta + bE_y v_2 / \delta - (b\delta/2)d\tau/dx - K_2 d\theta_2 / dx + bq \\ C_2 d^2 u_2 / dx^2 + D_2 d^2 \theta_2 / dx^2 &= K_2 \theta_2 - bt_2 \tau / 2 + K_2 dv_2 / dx\end{aligned}$$

The obtained equations are the complete set of equations determining unknown quantities - $u_1, v_1, \theta_1, \tau, u_2, v_2, \theta_2$. This set of equations is the fourteenth order with respect to variable x . Accordingly, seven boundary conditions must be formulated at each beam edge. The equations (48) are rather universal, and take into account the transverse shear deformation and laminated structure of the facings as well as the compressibility of the orthotropic core.

Now consider the sandwich beam with the homogeneous uniform facings, which is widely met in practice. In accordance with Eqs.(23), (25) and(33), we have

$$B_1 = B_2 = B = E_{fx}bt \quad D_1 = D_2 = D = E_{fx}bt^3/12 \quad K_1 = K_2 = K = G_{fxy}bt \quad C_1 = C_2 = 0 \quad (49)$$

where $t = t_1 = t_2 \quad E_{fx} = E_{1x} = E_{2x} \quad G_{fxy} = G_{1xy} = G_{2xy}$

Substituting Eqs.(49) into Eqs.(48), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}Bd^2 u_1 / dx^2 &= b\tau \\ Kd^2 v_1 / dx^2 &= bE_y v_1 / \delta - bE_y v_2 / \delta - (b\delta/2)d\tau/dx - Kd\theta_1 / dx - bp \\ Dd^2 \theta_1 / dx^2 &= K\theta_1 - bt\tau / 2 + Kdv_1 / dx \\ (\delta^3 / 12E_y) d^2 \tau / dx^2 &= -u_1 + \theta_1 t / 2 + u_2 + \theta_2 t / 2 + \delta\tau / G_{xy} - (\delta/2)dv_1 / dx - (\delta/2)dv_2 / dx \\ Bd^2 u_2 / dx^2 &= -b\tau \\ Kd^2 v_2 / dx^2 &= -bE_y v_1 / \delta + bE_y v_2 / \delta - (b\delta/2)d\tau/dx - Kd\theta_2 / dx + bq \\ Dd^2 \theta_2 / dx^2 &= K\theta_2 - bt\tau / 2 + Kdv_2 / dx\end{aligned}\quad (50)$$

Let us rewrite the set of Eqs.(50) in the following matrix form

$$d^2 \mathbf{U} / dx^2 = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{U} + \mathbf{B} d\mathbf{U} / dx + \mathbf{P} \quad (51)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{U} &= \{u_1, v_1, \theta_1, \tau, u_2, v_2, \theta_2\}^T \\ \mathbf{P} &= \{0, -p/(G_{fxy}t), 0, 0, 0, q/(G_{fxy}t), 0\}^T\end{aligned}\quad (52)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/(E_{fx}t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & E_y/(G_{fxy}\delta t) & 0 & 0 & 0 & -E_y/(G_{fxy}\delta t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 12G_{fxy}/(E_{fx}t^2) & -6/(E_{fx}t^2) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -12E_y/\delta^3 & 0 & 6E_y t/\delta^3 & 12E_y/(G_{xy}\delta^2) & -12E_y/\delta^3 & 0 & -6E_y t/\delta^3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1/(E_{fx}t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -E_y/(G_{fxy}\delta t) & 0 & 0 & 0 & E_y/(G_{fxy}\delta t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -6/(E_{fx}t^2) & 0 & 0 & 12G_{fxy}/(E_{fx}t^2) \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & -\delta/(2tG_{fxy}) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 12G_{fxy}/(E_{fx}t^2) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -6E_y/\delta^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -6E_y/\delta^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\delta/(2tG_{fxy}) & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 12G_{fxy}/(E_{fx}t^2) & 0 \end{Bmatrix}$$

Let us use the Abramov sweep method [10] for solution of the differential equations (51). For this purpose, let us transform the set (51) into the first-order set of differential equations

$$d\mathbf{Y}/dx = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{Y} + \mathbf{G} \quad (53)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{Y} = \{\mathbf{Y}_1, \mathbf{Y}_2\}^T \quad \mathbf{Y}_1 = \mathbf{U} \quad \mathbf{Y}_2 = d\mathbf{U}/dx \quad (54)$$

$$\text{and } \mathbf{F} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{G} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_1 \\ \mathbf{P} \end{Bmatrix}$$

Here, \mathbf{I} is the 7×7 identify matrix, $\mathbf{0}$ is the 7×7 zero matrix and $\mathbf{0}_1$ is the 7×1 zero vector. The set (53) should be supplemented with the boundary conditions for $x=0$ and $x=l$. The boundary conditions can be presented by the following algebraic equations

$$\mathbf{H}_0 \mathbf{Y}_0 = \mathbf{R}_0 \quad \mathbf{H}_l \mathbf{Y}_l = \mathbf{R}_l \quad (55)$$

Here, $\mathbf{Y}_0 = \mathbf{Y}(0)$, $\mathbf{Y}_l = \mathbf{Y}(l)$, \mathbf{H}_0 , \mathbf{H}_l are the 7×14 given matrixes and \mathbf{R}_0 , \mathbf{R}_l are the 7×1 given vectors. The differential equations (53) and the boundary conditions (55) generate the boundary-value problem of the sandwich beam model under consideration.

Completing this section, let us establish a correspondence between the components of the \mathbf{Y} vector and the required functions. Taking into account Eqs.(52), (54), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} y_1 = u_1 \quad y_2 = v_1 \quad y_3 = \theta_1 \quad y_4 = \tau \quad y_5 = u_2 \quad y_6 = v_2 \quad y_7 = \theta_2 \quad y_8 = du_1/dx \\ y_9 = dv_1/dx \quad y_{10} = d\theta_1/dx \quad y_{11} = d\tau/dx \quad y_{12} = du_2/dx \quad y_{13} = dv_2/dx \quad y_{14} = d\theta_2/dx \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

Now express the forces and moments, acting in the facings in terms of $y_i (i=1,14)$. Using Eqs.(18), (19), (22), (24), (31), (32), (49) and (56), we have

$$N_1 = By_8 \quad Q_1 = K(y_3 + y_9) \quad M_1 = Dy_{10} \quad N_2 = By_{12} \quad Q_2 = K(y_7 + y_{13}) \quad M_2 = Dy_{14} \quad (57)$$

Numerical study

The numerical analyses of the stress-strain state of the sandwich beam for various loading cases and boundary conditions are presented in this section. The sandwich beam consists of two identical homogeneous facings and orthotropic core. The beam length l is $0.1m$, the facings thickness t is $0.001m$ and the core thickness δ is $0.018m$. The characteristics of the materials are as follows: $E_{fx} = 20000MPa$, $G_{fxy} = 200MPa$, $E_y = 300MPa$ and $G_{xy} = 50MPa$.

By way of the first example let us consider the cantilevered sandwich beam loaded by uniform pressure $p = 1MPa$, applied at the upper and the lower face sheets (Fig.6).

Fig.6. The cantilevered sandwich beam loaded by uniform pressure applied at the upper and lower face sheets.

The boundary conditions have the form

$$\begin{aligned} \text{for } x=0 \quad & u_1=0 \quad v_1=0 \quad \theta_1=0 \quad \tau=0 \quad u_2=0 \quad v_2=0 \quad \theta_2=0 \\ \text{for } x=l \quad & N_1=0 \quad Q_1=0 \quad M_1=0 \quad \tau=0 \quad N_2=0 \quad Q_2=0 \quad M_2=0 \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

Express the boundary conditions in terms of $y_i (i=1,14)$. Using Eqs.(56), (57), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \text{for } x=0 \quad & y_1=0 \quad y_2=0 \quad y_3=0 \quad y_4=0 \quad y_5=0 \quad y_6=0 \quad y_7=0 \\ \text{for } x=l \quad & y_8=0 \quad y_3+y_9=0 \quad y_{10}=0 \quad y_4=0 \quad y_{12}=0 \quad y_7+y_{13}=0 \quad y_{14}=0 \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

The \mathbf{H}_0 , \mathbf{H}_l matrixes and the \mathbf{R}_0 , \mathbf{R}_l vectors take the form

$$\mathbf{H}_0 = \begin{Bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{H}_l = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (60)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_0 = \mathbf{R}_l = \{0,0,0,0,0,0,0\}^T \quad (61)$$

The results in the form of deflections v_1 , v_2 and the stress σ in the core appear on Fig.7.

Fig.7. Distributions of the deflections v_1 , v_2 and the stress σ

It is notable, that the range of the functions v_1 , v_2 , σ reminds one of the boundary-layer effect taking place at the axisymmetric deformation of the circular cylindrical shell. That range of the functions cannot be received within the framework of model not taking into account the compressibility of the core.

The second example studies the cantilevered sandwich beam loaded by uniform pressure $p = 1 \text{ MPa}$ applied at the upper facing (Fig.8).

Fig.8. The cantilevered sandwich beam loaded by uniform pressure applied at the upper face sheet.

The boundary conditions in this example coincide with the boundary conditions of the first example (60),(61). The ratio v_1/v_2 and the σ stress are shown in Fig.9. It is seen from Fig.9 that the deflection of the lower facing is less than the deflection of the upper facing. It is obvious, that the more pliable the core the bigger the difference in the deflections

Fig.9. Distributions the ratio v_1/v_2 and the σ stress

By way of the third example let us consider the cantilevered sandwich beam loaded by transverse forces T applied at the free edges of both facings (Fig.10).

Fig.10 . The cantilevered sandwich beam loaded by transverse forces applied at the free edges of both facings.

Let $T/b = 10^5 \text{ N/m}$. The boundary conditions for $x=0$ coincide with the boundary conditions of the first and second examples. The boundary conditions for $x=l$ have the form

$$N_1 = 0 \quad Q_1 = T \quad M_1 = 0 \quad \tau = 0 \quad N_2 = 0 \quad Q_2 = -T \quad M_2 = 0$$

or $y_8 = 0 \quad y_3 + y_9 = \alpha \quad y_{10} = 0 \quad y_4 = 0 \quad y_{12} = 0 \quad y_7 + y_{13} = -\alpha \quad y_{14} = 0 \quad \alpha = T/(G_{fx}tb)$.

By this means, the \mathbf{H}_0 , \mathbf{H}_l matrixes are defined by the relationships (60). The \mathbf{R}_0 vector is the zero vector and $\mathbf{R}_l = \{0, \alpha, 0, 0, 0, -\alpha, 0\}^T$. The v_1 , v_2 deflections and the σ stress are shown in Fig.11.

Fig.11. Distributions of the deflections v_1 , v_2 and the stress σ

The fourth example is the sandwich beam with clamped edges of the lower facing and loaded by longitudinal force N at the free edge of the upper facing (Fig.12).

Fig.12 . The beam with clamped edges of the lower facing loaded by force at the free edge of the upper facing.

Let $N/b = 10^5 \text{ N/m}$. The boundary conditions may be expressed thus:

$$\text{for } x=0 \quad N_1 = 0 \quad Q_1 = 0 \quad M_1 = 0 \quad \tau = 0 \quad u_2 = 0 \quad v_2 = 0 \quad \theta_2 = 0$$

$$\text{for } x=l \quad N_1 = N \quad Q_1 = 0 \quad M_1 = 0 \quad \tau = 0 \quad u_2 = 0 \quad v_2 = 0 \quad \theta_2 = 0$$

or using Eqs.(56),(57) as follows

$$\text{for } x=0 \quad y_8 = 0 \quad y_3 + y_9 = 0 \quad y_{10} = 0 \quad y_4 = 0 \quad y_5 = 0 \quad y_6 = 0 \quad y_7 = 0$$

$$\text{for } x=l \quad y_8 = \beta \quad y_3 + y_9 = 0 \quad y_{10} = 0 \quad y_4 = 0 \quad y_5 = 0 \quad y_6 = 0 \quad y_7 = 0 \quad \beta = N/(E_{fx}tb)$$

The \mathbf{H}_0 , \mathbf{H}_l matrixes have the form

$$\mathbf{H}_0 = \mathbf{H}_l = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{Bmatrix}$$

The \mathbf{R}_0 vector is the zero vector and $\mathbf{R}_l = \{\beta, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0\}^T$. The results throughout the beam length appear in Fig.13.

Fig.13. Distributions of the displacements and the stresses throughout the beam length

CONCLUSIONS

The computational model of sandwich beam is developed. The beam one-dimensional model by virtue of its relative simplicity is useful for preliminary analyses of the more complicated two-dimensional sandwich structures. Within the framework of this model, the transverse shear strain and laminated structure of the facings as well as the compressibility of the core are taken into account. The final set of the governing differential equations has 14-th order. The Abramov sweep method has been used to solution of the formulated problem. The Fortran computer program, realizing sweep method has been developed. The numerical analysis of the stress-strain state of the sandwich beam for various loading cases and boundary conditions has been performed. Analysis of the results show that proposed model of the sandwich beam allows to solve problems of the determination of the deformation pattern that could not be solved using traditional models.

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